

1. Head of the planthopper, showing the characteristic vertical bands.

2. Head of the BPH.

The head of the planthopper shows vertical black bands on the frons (Fig. 1). These appear to be its characteristic feature, and are not seen in BPH (Fig. 2). The ventral side of the abdomen in the 4th- and 5th-instar nymphs shows a pair of distinct black spots laterally on either side near the 5th segment.

Specimens have been identified as *Toya* spp. by CAB International Institute of Entomology, London.

Although ricefields adjacent to the Sewage Farm were not infested with this planthopper, adult females caged after 5 h of starvation on 40-d-old IR50 rice seedlings were found to thrive for the next 56 h.

Usually, the planthopper moves more swiftly than BPH, but becomes less active after a starvation period. Insects

regain their natural poise after a few hours on rice plants, indicating possible force-feeding. Actual feeding experiments on rice seedlings showed a mean weight of 7.0 mg honeydew/adult as against 22.7 mg on the regular host.

No survival occurred among 40 freshly hatched nymphs confined on 35-d-old IR50 rice seedlings.

After 56 h on rice plants, the insects had oviposited an average 26 eggs/ insect, in batches of 6-9 eggs. □

Chemical control of thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* in the rice nursery

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Spray formulations of phosphamidon, monocrotophos, phosalone, chlorpyrifos, metasystox, endosulfan, dimethoate, and neem oil were evaluated for control of rice thrips in the rice nursery. The field experiment with nine treatments including control was

laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

Pregerminated seeds of IR20 were sown in 0.5-m² plots. Thrips infestation was noticed 10 d after sowing and pretreatment counts were taken on 15 randomly selected seedlings. Counts were taken at 24, 48, and 72 h, and 1 wk, and 2 wk after treatment.

All chemicals were significantly effective in controlling thrips (see table). Chlorpyrifos, dimethoate, and monocrotophos were best. Although neem oil did not reduce thrips population significantly 24 h after application, it did reduce population at 48 and 72 h after application. □

Effect of insecticides for thrips control.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment	Population ^b (no.)						
	Pretreatment	24 h	48 h	72 h	1 wk	2 wk	Mean
Phosalone (0.07%)	5.9	0.2 ab	0.9 ab	0.4 a	1.4 b	4.5 d	1.7 b
Chlorpyrifos (0.04%)	5.1	1.1 ab	0.9 b	0.7 abc	0.7 a	1.2 a	0.9 a
Monocrotophos (0.04%)	6.6	0.9 a	0.3 a	0.4 a	1.5 b	3.1 c	1.2 a
Metasystox (0.04%)	6.9	1.7 b	0.6 ab	0.5 ab	1.8 b	3.4 c	1.6 b
Dimethoate (0.04%)	5.2	1.2 ab	0.6 ab	0.5 a	0.6 a	1.9 b	0.9 a
Phosphamidon (0.04%)	5.4	1.7 b	0.9 b	0.9 abc	0.9 abc	3.6 c	1.8 b
Endosulfan (0.05%)	5.4	2.5 c	1.6 c	1.0 c	1.9 c	4.8 d	2.4 c
Neem oil (2.0%)	5.7	4.9 d	1.8 c	1.4 d	2.3 c	4.3 d	2.9 d
Control	5.7	4.8 d	5.8 d	6.4 e	7.6 d	7.8 e	6.5 e
Period mean		2.2 b	1.5 a	1.4 a	2.2 b	3.8 c	

^aMean of 45 seedlings. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level. In a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different by DMRT at the 5% level.

Alternate ricefield hosts of the Angoumois grain moth

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The Angoumois grain moth *Sitotroga cerealella* is an important pest of rice,

wheat, barley, millet, and maize. Field infestation is carried to storage, where it causes severe losses in quality and quantity.

Field infestation on different hosts can identify source of inoculum for rice and other cereals. In places where rice is grown in a particular season, the pest may survive on alternate hosts in other seasons to reinfest the next rice crop.

Information on field infestation also will help determine prophylactic sprays in endemic areas or help in devising an appropriate Angoumois grain moth management system for rice.

We collected 10 panicles/plot at random from 6 fields of sorghum, pearl millet, and maize 1 wk before harvest Jan-Feb 1986. Ten 100-g samples of rice were collected from 12 plots at harvest

and at threshing. Hundreds of panicles of weeds on ricefield bunds were collected from 10 plots. The samples were stored in plastic containers in the laboratory and moth emergence observed after 1 mo.

Field infestation was found in rice, sorghum, maize, pearl millet, and the weed *Echinochloa colona*. The occurrence of *S. cerealella* on pearl

millet and *E. colona* are new records of field infestation.

The number of moths that emerged was highest in pearl millet (26-32/panicle), followed by sorghum (18-20) and maize (6-12). Moth emergence in rice was 3-8/100 g. The lowest number of moths (4/100 panicles) emerged in *E. colona*, and they were very small (1.0-1.5 mm long). □

Susceptibility of field strains of smaller brown planthopper (SBPH) in Taiwan to six insecticides

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Before 1984, only carbofuran was recommended to control SBPH in Taiwan; SBPH had been considered a secondary pest of rice. However, during the last few years, SBPH incidence has resulted in serious damage to rice in central and southern parts of the island. Carbofuran, buprofezin, and flucythrinate have been commonly used for control.

We studied susceptibility of four field strains of SBPH to six insecticides.

An acetone solution of 4-5 concentrations of each insecticide was sprayed onto 4th-instar nymphs. Each concentration had 3 replications; 45 insects were tested. When a synergist was used, the nymphs were sprayed with an acetone solution of the synergist 1 h before insecticide treatment. Mortality was recorded 24 h after treatment.

Flucythrinate and fenvalerate were the most effective insecticides (see table). (Note that both pyrethroids have an α -isopropylphenyl group in their acid moiety.) Cypermethrin exhibited intermediate effectiveness against SBPH, and permethrin was considerably less potent. Carbofuran appeared less toxic than all pyrethroids except permethrin. Malathion was practically useless.

Limited synergism data showed that the toxicity of permethrin could be enhanced about 50 times by tributyl

Susceptibility of 4 field strains of SBPH in Taiwan to 6 insecticides.

Insecticide ^a	Field strain LC ₅₀ ^b (µg/ml)			
	Ping-tung	Tai-chung	Chia-yi	I-lang
Permethrin	1,272	2,531	693	2,093
+ TBPT	25.3 (50)	49.1 (52)	—	—
+ PB	510 (2.5)	212 (12)	—	—
Cypermethrin	25.9	41.7	43.0	13.1
+ TBPT	5.6 (3.6)	14.1 (3.0)	—	—
+ PB	4.8 (5.4)	—	—	—
Fenvalerate	—	7.1	6.0	10.2
Flucythrinate	3.9	55	3.9	15.1
Carbofuran	—	96.9	52.4	61.6
Malathion	3,458	5343	10,129	4,120

^aTBPT = tributyl phosphorotrithioate, at 50 µg/ml. PB = piperonyl butoxide, at 25 µg/ml. ^bFigures in parentheses represent LC₅₀ of unsynergized insecticide/LC₅₀ of synergized insecticide.

phosphorotrithioate, an inhibitor of esterases. Synergism of permethrin by piperonyl butoxide, which inhibits microsomal oxidases, was limited. Synergism of cypermethrin by either synergist was not as significant as that of permethrin.

In view of these results, we suggest that SBPH in Taiwan has become resistant to malathion and permethrin but remains susceptible to fenvalerate, flucythrinate, and cypermethrin.

Resistance to permethrin, and very possibly to malathion, is closely related to hydrolytic degradation by esterases. This resistance mechanism resembles that we found earlier in the brown planthopper (BPH). In BPH, high esterase activity associated with organophosphorus and carbamate resistance may have conferred a major part of the resistance to permethrin and other primary alcohol ester pyrethroids. □

Managing other pests

Ufra - a first report in Orissa, India

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Ufra caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* has been recorded for the first time in

Orissa. It was found on tall indica local variety Rangi in Dapa village, Balasore District, usually a deepwater rice area. However, in 1987 the habitat was atypical, with only a few centimeters standing water in the field because of the unusual drought. Affected plants are stunted with withered boot leaf and sheath. Panicles are very much reduced